

Personal Essay

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My interest and philosophy of nursing directly comes from the interest in this field and I have desires to help people. I choose this profession because I am around people who need help and they get internal satisfaction when I take care of them. I did many volunteer works in my life and it brings me an internal happiness. I believe that cure for any diseases is not just the medicine but it is the love, affection and care we give to them. this is the stage in my life where I believe that I can make difference in my professional life and I did my LPN and continuing my job and then enrolled in RN program to further enhance my skills and abilities in this field.

My nursing career started from November 200, when I worked as the Phlebotomist till August 2009. The overall time frame of this job was exciting and I learned lots of things in these years. The interest and love for the subject increased so much that I decide to join LPN school where I can learn and enhance my skills in field of nursing. From August 2009 till November 2010 I join the LPN school as full time student in order to concentrate completely on my studies. The education process was a good journey and I learned lots of things which I applied in my clinics and practices. In enrolment of LPN program I submitted my high school diploma because it is good for enrolling in this program and prospective employers prefer candidates who have a formal education.

I also attend an accredited LPN program and my favorite subjects were biology, communications, physiology and clinical care. The exam permit was given by National Council for Nurses (NCLEX-PN). The NCLEX-PN is a standardized test that measures

both clinical skills and nursing practice. In some health care settings, such as home care, an LPN may work with a nurse, but in institutional settings such as hospitals and skilled nursing, LPN nurses generally take orders on different various movements, or even several time nurses, depending on how the structures facilitated its workflow.

Consequently, I worked as assistant in my clinical practices in the same system, which can find them work differently and two assistants in two different institutions will most likely have different protocols for patient care.

The important and most controversial aspects and most diverse of the LPN practice involves the care plans. The National Council of State Boards of Nursing also recommends this practice. However, even New York allows LPNs to take part in the development of supervision plans. Therefore, I learned to make decisions based on data from patient health data and other psychological factors and then make changes to self care plans.

In my opinion and analysis the principle and values of a nurse is very important for the work exerted in this profession since, because of these ethical, aesthetic and social are human virtues. Therefore, I am strictly attached to this principle and I follow these guidelines throughout my nursing career. I possess the skills of ethical consideration, aesthetic and social principles, which makes an important collection of virtues important for practicing in the nursing profession.

I also have the qualities such as honesty, truthfulness, responsibility, fairness, affection, kindness, discipline, cooperation, commitment, creativity, discretion, choice, fairness, initiative, loyalty, observation, patience, perception, neatness, reflection, service, solidarity, kindness, and behavior, which attributes are important in training, and

personality of a nurse practitioner. These are qualities that are acquired fitted on the shaft methodological training, and within them professionalism staff should maintain prudence and strength, without them there is no possible virtue (choose good is prudence, not abandon, is that despite the obstacles of passion and pride, strength constitute).

After completing my LPN program I was having many options to continue my education and work as well. Therefore I decided to start the RN program which was a good option because I worked in nursing homes. Beside that I also completed certification, which I got right after my graduation. In addition to that I also did certification in HIV/AIDS.

Currently I am enrolled in RN program and hopefully I will be graduating in August 2014. The RN program enhances my skills in making effective observations in my practices. the observation in my opinion requires certain characteristics which includes the expediency - to observe the strict definition of nursing: an entity (ward) and object (the scope and nature) observation; regularity - definition of the observation plan and its implementation in a specific period of time; objectivity - unbiased perception and recording of facts which are the basis for interpreting the observations, as well as verification of other data obtained by means of, for example, interviews, document analysis and measurement; and selectivity - focusing attention on observing the most relevant and important phenomena and behavior of the patient and his family in the patient's medical situation.

My principles of observation in my career are establishing and maintaining a two-sided, verbal and non-verbal contact with the patient and determining the purpose or purposes of observation. In my view the observation should be of the most objective

(impartial) and should be monitored discreetly. The information obtained by observation should be noted in the patient history and any uncertain information should be verified by other methods. I also possess the skills of respect, dignity, privacy and individuality of the patient. Throughout my life I think manifestation of the patient's attitude towards kindness, patience, fostering a climate of mutual trust and understanding and guarantee the right to protection of personal data of the patient.

I am working as Medical Services Coordinator and my nature of job is to coordinating and supervising the work of other professionals and technicians in health sciences (general medicine, specialized dentistry and psychology) as part of the health care business. Generally my activities include running the assigned activities in accordance with the laws, policies, rules and regulations that govern your area, so you must be constantly updated. Developing and promulgating policies, rules and procedures for the medical services of the company. Plan, organize and execute diagnostic analysis and professionals in the field of Occupational Medicine. Providing medical care and monitoring officers of the Company or family members, who need it, perform or recommend therapy or surgical procedures and studies applicable to each case. Maintaining a data bank or data to support or facilitate their work and that of other colleagues who work in the company.

I also conduct and supervise research projects in the field of Occupational Medicine. Advising Occupational Health Committees and First Response Brigades aspects of first aid and occupational health and collaborate with other units of the Human Resources Division and the Departments of Integral Protection of different managements in these aspects. Providing professional technical supervision to medical services of

various company sites, and evaluating the performance of medical services personnel and monitor compliance of the work programs. Developing, implementing and monitoring investment budgets and operations for the area of health. Assessing the needs of medicines, equipment and materials for medical services and prepare the annual procurement plan.

Performing and coordinating training for medical and nursing staff. Providing educational talks in the health field and performing administrative tasks to be deriving from it. Ensuring proper operation and use of the facilities, equipment and instruments used in the development activities, reporting any abnormality or injury that is submitted to his immediate superior. Providing cooperation in situations of risk and losses that arise in the company and actively participating, cooperating and complying with all policies, procedures and regulations relating to quality assurance to develop and implement the company.

Lastly, I am pleased with my career and professional life as this gives me internal happiness by helping others. I have the qualities of honesty, truthfulness, responsibility, affection, kindness, discipline, and cooperation which are important attributes to grow in this field. These are qualities that are acquired fitted on the shaft methodological training, and within them professionalism staff should maintain prudence and strength, without them there is no possible virtue. In my nursing career I plan and implement my principles which are in accordance with law and always tried to follow them. I have decided to continue growing in this field by having more certification and gaining more experiences in my professional life.

References

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